

MENTAL DISORDERS IN RELATIVES PATIENTS WITH COVID-19

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Abstract: The large flow of information and the breaking of established stereotypes of life before the pandemic sharply reduce each individual's resistance to negative influences towards the development of anxiety, fear, and depression. This paper presents the results of a study regarding mental disorders in close relatives of patients with COVID-19, the features of their manifestation, and the causes of their occurrence.

Keywords: anxiety, fear, post-traumatic stress disorder, pandemic, self-isolation, emotions, adaptation.

Currently, many studies are being carried out in different countries on the impact of the epidemiological situation on the mental state of humans, and at present it is considered very relevant and socially significant.

The COVID-19 pandemic, like all other negative processes on the global scale, - negatively affected the general mental state of people and caused anxiety disorders, chronic stress, and other reactive States. This in turn creates new challenges for medical workers involved in psychoprophylaxis and the mental health of the population.

Literature analysis and methodology. Studies showing a link between the epidemiological situation and negative mental states have been previously conducted by several experts. As you know, there is a relationship between the pandemic regime and alarming disorders in people, depression, and an increase in the level of post-traumatic stress disorder. This includes a very wide range of people, that is, those who are directly infected, work with sick people, relatives of patients, etc. For example, studies have found that Ebola fever affects the growth of anxiety disorders and phobias in those who survive infection [13; B.671-691], aggression, and capricious thoughts [14; B.12784-12791.], depression [11; B.11. 13; B.12784-12791.], guilt [13; B.671-691], and posttraumatic stress disorder [10; B.1-3] which led to an increase in the likes. A similar condition occurs in the following, H1N1 influenza anxiety [16; B.353-360.], intense fatigue among physicians [16; B. 353-360.] and the effect on increased stress; The effect of Zika virus on increased fear in mothers of newborns [5; B.1149-1151.]; The effect of SARS on increased stress [7; B.15.], posttraumatic stress disorder [9; B.123-135], and increased anxiety [7; B.15.] identified.

Discussion. Thanks to the study of different groups of the population, it is possible to assess the socio-psychological state of society and then use the information obtained to provide psychological assistance. The COVID-19 pandemic can have various socio-psychological consequences. In addition, one of the most pressing issues for the science and practice of psychology is quarantine (anxiety, loss of control, panic attacks, fears, neurotic disorders, substance abuse, decreased critical thinking skills, and belief in "supernatural" things; distrust of social institutions, Authorities, media, etc.) remains a matter of the mental state and behavior of isolated people. Of course, this problem is important for determining the directions

for providing mental support in the practical activities of a psychiatrist and determining the factors that should be taken into account in the construction of psychotherapeutic and counseling work.

Traditionally, research on the impact of the pandemic on the mental state of people can be divided into several categories: the impact of the pandemic on people who are part of the risk group - those who are in close contact with COVID-19 patients (for example, medical workers), as well as on people who have certain diseases and need help; the study.

Research on the impact of the pandemic on at-risk individuals is the most relevant and widespread. Thus, in the current epidemiological situation, difficulties arose in providing regular specialized assistance to individuals with psychiatric diagnoses. In foreign Psychiatry, this phenomenon is often referred to as "partial deprivation syndrome" [6; B.12.] and described as a decrease or cessation or stimulation of social, cognitive, and physical activity in patients with mental pathology, etc. Adolescents, in particular, patients are close relatives of this syndrome [6; B.15. 8; B.8. 17; B.580-585.] and seniors in need of socio-medical resources are considered sensitive. Drastic changes in normal daily activities can be a stressful phenomenon both for the patients themselves and for their loved ones, which increases anxiety and leads to a decrease in the emotional background [3; B.922-931].

The purpose of the study. The purpose of the study was to study the clinical features of mental disorders in relatives of patients with COVID-19 and develop a treatment and rehabilitation strategy based on the data obtained.

120 patients with mental illness, aged 18 to 55 years, relatives of COVID-19 patients, were selected as the objects of the study. Patients underwent medical examinations in 2020-2022 at the city psychoneurological dispensary, the city clinical psychiatric hospital, and The Tashkent City Republican psychiatric clinic. All examined patients were divided into 2 groups: Group 1-the main group, relatives of patients with mental disorders, COVID-19 (n=75); Group 2-control group, patients with mental disorders who do not have COVID-19 in their relatives (n=45).

Demographic data from patients who participated in the study, physical symptoms from the last 14 days, a history of COVID-19 cases in relatives, concerns about COVID-19, precautions against the virus, and additional data related to COVID-19 were collected. The study also used the DASS Depression Scale and the IES-R traumatic event effect scale.

As the social-demographic indicators were taken into account in this study, the following were taken into account: gender, age, availability of children, marital status, student status, and availability or absence of work.

Results. A total of 53.8% of respondents rated the psychological effects of the virus outbreak as moderate to severe; 16.5% reported moderate to severe depressive symptoms; 28.8% reported moderate to severe anxiety symptoms and 8.1% reported moderate to severe stress.

The majority of respondents spent 20-24 hours a day at home (84.7%); were worried about family members contracting COVID-19 (75.2%); satisfied with the availability of medical information (75.1%). Up-to-date and accurate health data (treatments, case statistics, etc.) and special precautions (hand hygiene, wearing a mask) have been associated with lower levels of stress, anxiety, and depression ($P < 0.05$).

Men in the study received a lower score on the scale of posttraumatic stress disorder symptoms than women ($B = -0.20.95\%$; $CI: 0.35-0.05$), but on the stress subfield ($B = 0.10.95\%$; $CI: 0.02-0.19$), anxiety subfield ($B = 0.19$; $CI: 0.05-0.33$), and depression subfield ($B = 0.12$; $CI: 0.01-0.23$) with higher rates.

The study also found significant correlations between student status and higher levels of posttraumatic stress disorder symptoms ($B = 0.20$; $CI: 0.05-0.35$), stress subfield ($B = 0.11$; $CI: 0.02 -0.19$), and DASS

anxiety subfield ($B = 0.16$; CI: 0.02—0.30). Such contacts with a group of working persons were not found. It was not found that signs of post-traumatic stress disorder were associated with severity and other socio-demographic indicators such as the age of depression, the presence of children, marital status, and the presence or absence of work. The study also found that dissatisfaction with the amount of available medical data on COVID-19 was significantly correlated with higher rates of posttraumatic stress disorder symptoms ($B = 0.63$; CI: 0.11-1.14) and stress subspace ($B = 0.32$; ci: 0.02-0.62). It has been found that information about the increase in the number of individuals with recovered health is significantly correlated with low scores of stress sub channel indicators ($B = -0.24$; c I: -0.40-0.07).

It is worth noting that the coverage of various issues related to COVID-19 in the media is highlighted as an important factor affecting the mental state of people. Media and internet resources are available precautions in an epidemiological situation, Self-Help methods, disease ratios, sick and recovering people, etc. allow you to get information about. The study of the influence of the media on the mental state of people is also very relevant.

The clinical diagnosis of personality types in the study was created on the basis of the standardized multifactorial method of personality learning (SMOL) 2004 L.N. Sobchik and V.P. A mini-mult adapted by the Zaitsev was detected using a shortened version. Table 1.

Table 1 Distribution of patients by personality types

Type of person	I group (n=75)		II group (n=45)	
	Abs.	%	Abs.	%
Asthenic	2	2,7	0	0
Psychoasthenic	6	8,0	3	6,7
Schizoid	0	0	1	2,2
Cycloid	4	5,3	2	4,4
Epileptoid	3	4,0	5	11,1
Histrionic	5	5,7	11	24,4*
Unstable	45	60,0	13	31,1**
Paranoid	0	0	1	2,2
Conformist	10	13,3	9	20,0
Total	75	100,0	45	100,0

Note: differences are significant with respect to * - Group II data (* - $P < 0.05$; ** - $P < 0.01$); differences are significant with respect to ^ - Group III data (^ - $P < 0.05$; ^^ - $P < 0.001$)

The Unstable personality type is a passion for entertainment, unwillingness to be under the control of the mother, a desire for idleness, and a tendency to quickly succumb to the influence of another person. At the same time, the proportion of patients with abnormal personality type turned out to be significantly higher among patients of Group I (60.0% of patients of Group I; 31.1% of patients of Group II ($P_{1-2} < 0.01$) and 18.8% of patients).

Unlike the irregular type, the frequency of occurrence of representatives of the conformal personality type did not make Intergroup differences (13.3% of patients in the group). I; 20.0% of Group II patients ($P_{1-2} > 0.05$). O'zga yuqori baho beruvchi, etakchilikka va diqqat markazida bo'lishga intilish bilan xarakterlanuvchi isterik shaxs turi II guruh bemorlariga xos bo'ldi (I guruh bemorlarining 5,7%; II guruh bemorlarining 24,4% ($P_{1-2} < 0,05$)).

Thus, the results on the relationship between the use of media in the population and the manifestation of anxiety and depression in relatives of patients with the disease showed the following. In the survey, respondents showed how many hours a day they spend on average in the media, and how many of these

hours are dedicated to the COVID-19 problem. An adult phobic weight scale (DSM-5 Severity-Measure-For-Specific-Phobia-Adult-Scale) and a health status scale (PHQ-4) were used to identify anxiety disorders and depressive tendencies.

The study found that there is a direct correlation between phobia symptoms in adults, media use time, and anxiety symptoms ($r = 0.25$; $P < 0.001$). Also, according to the health status scale (PHQ-4), a direct correlation was found between media use time and anxiety symptoms ($R = 0.20$; $p < 0.001$) and depression ($R = 0.19$; $p < 0.001$). Thus, the longer subjects devote to media studies on issues related to COVID-19, the higher the average rates of anxiety and depression symptoms.

In addition, respondents who reported using official government or community health websites as a primary source of information about COVID-19 - had a much lower overall level of anxiety and depression symptoms than respondents who did not use such websites. (PHQ-4: $m = 4.08$; $SD = 3.12$ versus $M = 4.42$; $SD = 3.40$; $F(1, 6076) = 5.53$; $p = 0.019$). However, a group of respondents using official government websites is more likely than a group not using official websites ($M = 10.29$; $SD = 6.96$ and $M = 9.52$; $SD = 6.88$; $F(1, 61-76) = 13.56$, $p < 0.001$) phobia levels were higher. It is important to note that even before the pandemic, respondents who claimed to be afraid of physical illness expressed fear significantly more frequently ($M = 10.56$ and $M = 6.49$; $F(1, 5173) = 18.70$; $P < 0.001$) and longer than respondents who had no fear before the pandemic ($M = 2.82$ and $M = 2.30$ hours; $F(1, 5173) = 205.39$; $P < 0.001$) used media.

Conclusion. Summing up the results of a study on the impact of the pandemic and related factors on the mental state of people, the change in psychological state and behavior is conditionally possible even in healthy people [15; B.51-66. 12; B.11-17], as long as problems can also occur among people with infection in close relatives. These changes are mainly manifested in the form of anxiety disorders and increased depression. In addition, these indicators turned out to be very accurate, regardless of characteristic features such as gender and age. It is worth noting that the manifestation of mainly anxiety disorders, depression, and other mental disorders in patients who have been diagnosed with the disease in their loved ones is associated with an insufficient amount of information about COVID-19, as well as a lack of psychological support from social networks or media, while among people with whom the disease was not detected, it turned out The information obtained may be associated with the active discussion of the topic of COVID-19 in the media, the regular publication of new information about coronavirus infection, which can cause a feeling of insecurity, anxiety and fear of infection. In addition, the study shows that fake information about COVID-19 is common on social networks, which spreads more easily than reliable information [1; B.28-39. 4; B.922-931].

It can also be noted that high levels of personal anxiety can help increase information about COVID-19 in the media to alleviate their anxiety. We can assume that the most relevant and accurate medical data (on methods of treating and preventing infection, statistics of cases), obtained not from various media, but from official sources or medical personnel, will help to reduce the level of the disease. One of the important factors in dealing with negative emotions, anxiety, and stress, decreased emotional background is the high level of development of emotional intelligence, that is, the ability to understand the feelings of oneself and others and control them [2; B.55-63].

Thus, the study of the relationship between the mental state of people during the pandemic and emotional intelligence can be one of the directions for further research. Analyzing the results, we note that the relationship between the epidemiological situation, personal characteristics, the influence of the media, and the psychological state of the respondents was determined. The data obtained is of high practical importance since it can be used during the COVID-19 pandemic in the development of psychological recommendations for improving mental health, both for vulnerable segments of the population and for individuals belonging to the group of conditional norms. Consulting work based on the consideration of the factors described above can give significant results in lowering the level of anxiety, stress, symptoms of

depression, etc. Also, the data obtained will open up prospects for further research in this area and require verification of the results obtained.

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